

PARTHENOS

Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

D2.2 Report on the assessment of the education and training plans and activities

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1. Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable D2.2 “Report on the assessment of the education and training plans and activities”. It provides information on the assessment of the initial training plan (D7.1 Initial Training Plan) and activities developed by the PARTHENOS work package (WP) 7. A comprehensive report based on two assessment exercises is supplemented with additional input about the first implementations of the initial training plan and its assessment. The document is structured in chapters, as follows:

- Chapter 2 forms the introduction that summarises the link between work conducted in WP2 and WP7. In addition, the main aspects and outputs of the initial training plan are presented. Thus, this chapter provides information about the training plan development, the target groups, teaching contents and the modes of delivery.
- Chapter 3 presents the methodological approach for organising and collecting the training plan reviews.
- The main results of the assessment are to be found in chapter 4.
- This is followed by chapter 5 which contains a brief overview of the first implementations of the training derived from the plan followed by more detailed assessments of the four completed components
- Chapter 6 contains a list of abbreviations, 7 lists the tables and charts.
- Chapter 8, the Annex, is the questionnaire completed by the students who attended the Leipzig summer university workshop.

2. Introduction and Context

This deliverable is the result of the joint efforts of the PARTHENOS Task 2.4 members from the Academy of Athens, Trinity College Dublin, the University of Applied Sciences Potsdam, and University of Copenhagen. Work is led by the University of Applied Sciences Potsdam.

The objective of D2.2 is the assessment of the education and training plan and activities produced in WP7. The process of collecting and developing a plan for training and education is iterative with at least two reviews. Thus, the current version of the training plan is not in its final shape. Main aspects like training modules directed at the PARTHENOS community will be set up at a later stage of the project. It is Task 2.4's aim to support the development of the first version of the training plan by providing structured feedback on the plan and its initial implementation and proposing corrections or integrations if necessary. Further activities to refine and enhance the training plan will be conducted in WP7 itself during the course of the project. Deliverable D7.2 "Report on training and education activities and updated planning" will provide further insight into the implementation of the initial education and training plan after 24 months and will document the updated version of the planning according to amendments recommended in this report. The final report on training and education activities, D7.3 that includes all recommendations and adjustments, will be delivered at the end of the PARTHENOS project (after 48 months) and will provide a final assessment

2.1 Development of training plan

The PARTHENOS initial training plan has the stated objective of collecting information about common issues across the PARTHENOS infrastructure partners with regard to training, coaching and knowledge needs within an e-Humanities context. It aims at providing appropriate training and professional development opportunities for researchers at three career stages (early, mid and advanced career) and to build and promote best practice and policy documents regarding the formation and promotion of researchers carrying out their work in DARIAH and CLARIN, and within other partner infrastructure environments.

The PARTHENOS training plan is targeted at users of digital humanities (DH) research infrastructures (RIs). Therefore, it focusses on that specific aspect and does not address all

training needs within the wider digital humanities community. It concentrates on two levels of user needs: the ‘need to know about’ (awareness raising) and the ‘need to know how to do’ (skills building). This distinction is considered to be reasonable since the awareness of what infrastructures are and do is a significant barrier to their wider use. For this reason, the training plan aims, on one hand, to assist future users to successfully adopt their tools and services and, on the other hand, it also wants to direct potential users’ attention to the existence of research infrastructures and to understand why they might seek out and use an infrastructure in the first place.

The initial training plan starts with the context of the development and underlying principles that are guiding the training plan, defines the audiences for the PARTHENOS training, and lists teaching contents and modalities of delivery.

The plan has been developed in close cooperation between the PARTHENOS WP2 and WP7, where the work conducted in WP2 functions as one input of the plan¹.

Other inputs are derived from the following activities within WP7:

- Desk research to obtain an overview of training practices relating to the concerns of DH infrastructures.
- Requests from the PARTHENOS work package leaders regarding specific needs that may directly arise from project developments.
- Engagement with cognate projects regarding embedding opportunities within the wider DH training environment.
- Hosting of a two-day development workshop of WP7 partners, including representatives of the DARIAH Teach project.²

Given the resource restrictions within the PARTHENOS project, the training plan concentrates on asynchronous delivery of training, ‘train the trainers’ approaches and partnerships with other projects and initiatives to accomplish the maximum impact.

¹ The results of the work conducted in WP2 that influenced the initial training plan can be found in chapter 4 of „D2.1, Report on User Requirements”.

² For a detailed overview of the resources that formed the initial training plan see chapter 2 of “D7.1. Initial Training Plan).

2.2 Communities

Although PARTHENOS is a research infrastructure project, the training plan is conceived as far more broadly relevant than just to researchers only. Consequently, the plan is directed towards the following target groups:

- a. Researchers
- b. Content specialists in CHIs
- c. Technical developers/Computer Scientists
- d. Managers of institutions and projects³

2.3 Teaching contents

One main idea behind the initial training plan is to look at user needs on a macro scale and not to narrow down the perspective to the usage of tools and services only. Since training offers for RIs are often derived directly from what a certain project has developed, users are introduced to the new tools and/ or environments and are provided with training on how to work within the environments or how to use the tools. This very specific training is enhanced by the PARTHENOS training plan with more general modules that focus on the creation of knowledge, skills, and abilities on a macro level. Hence, the plan is split the training themes comprising two phases. “Phase 1” concentrates on the broad skills and approaches to understand what RIs do in general, what benefits they can create for the respective target groups and what kind of knowledge is needed to successfully work with RIs. “Phase 2” of the training plan will focus on the concrete outputs of the PARTHENOS work packages and the need for training and education that is related to them. Given the need for this work to progress sufficiently before training can be developed to support it, these developments will be framed only in the second version of the plan, which will be developed after project month 24.

The modules for “Phase 1” of the plan are as follows:

- **“Infrastructure 101”** – Main purpose: to introduce in layperson’s language the essential concepts underpinning a RI. It is structured according to learning objectives and small units of text and video, with references to additional sources for further information.

³ The elaborated description of the target groups can be found in chapter 4 of “D7.1 Initial training plan”.

- **Sharing Data With and Through Research Infrastructures** – Main purpose: to provide information about data exchange from both the research infrastructure and the cultural heritage institutional perspectives.
- **Humanistic Knowledge Creation and Research Processes** – Main purpose: the development of an understanding of the modes and basis for humanities knowledge creation.
- **Sustainability for RIs** – Main purpose: to share experience of the PARTHENOS cluster in the development and embedding of digital projects.

The requirements and outputs of the PARTHENOS work packages will be integrated into “Phase 2” of the training plan.

2.4 Delivery of training

It is explained in the plan that the main activities will concentrate on deriving maximum value from creating frameworks for curricula, asynchronously available baseline modules and ‘train the trainers’ opportunities (largely delivered in cooperation with other projects and networks).

3. Methodological Approach

The evaluation of the initial training plan has been realized in three different ways.

Input came from:

1. a discussion with experts,
2. peer review,
3. the PARTHENOS work package leaders.

These three approaches are described in the following section.

3.1 Virtual expert talk

The first step in the organization of the expert discussion was the identification of experienced persons in the field of research infrastructures. When selecting the experts, great importance was placed on the reflection of the four target groups of the training plan. So, each target group (researcher; content specialists in CHIs; technical developers/ computer scientists; managers of institutions and / or projects) was represented by at least one person that is not directly involved in the PARTHENOS project. Experts were invited via

e-mail, provided with the initial training plan and were asked to focus on one of the following topics:

1. How to set up a training plan (chapters 2 and 3 of the plan)
2. Target audiences (chapter 4 of the plan)
3. Teaching contents and implementation (chapters 5 and 6 of the plan).

In order to structure the discussion and get input from all participants, our experts were asked to each give a statement on one of the above topics.

The evaluation meeting took place via an Adobe Connect video conference. The Task 2.4 team participated together with the selected experts. For information on the experts' background see table 1 below.

Perspective according to training plan target groups	Topic to comment on	Experiences (selection)
CHI perspective	Topic 3	Researcher in the field of Library and Information Science; Projects: Data Service Infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities (DASISH), Digital Curator Vocational Education Europe (DigCurV), Humanities at Scale (HaS)
Management perspective	Topic 1	Manager of EU projects; Projects: Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH); Humanities at Scale (HaS)
Management perspective	Topic 3	Professor in language technology, head of university department; Projects: The EUROTRA Project

Researcher perspective	Topic 2	PhD in History and Archaeology with a specialization in History, lecturer in DH
Technical Developer / Computer Scientist	Topic 2	PhD in mathematics, technical head and co-manager of European project, Projects: Collaborative European Digital Archival Infrastructure (CENDARI), Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH), Humanities at Scale (HaS)

Table 1: Background of experts

3.2 Peer Review

In addition to the expert talk, a peer review assessment was organized to collect written feedback on the training plan. The same criteria applied for the peer review as mentioned for the expert talk. People were selected according to their experiences in RIs and matching the training plan target groups. They were provided with the training plan document and asked for a written assessment guided along the following questions:

- Section 3 of the training plan - Overarching Principles
 - Do you think the approach we have taken is a valid one?
 - Is there anything that we are missing that you think we should include?
 - Is there something we have included that you think is irrelevant?
- Section 4 of the training plan - Audiences
 - Do you think these audience types provide a useful set of categories?
 - Are there any audiences or communities that you think we have missed?
 - Are there any audiences or communities that we have included that you think are not relevant?

- Section 5 of the training plan - The Plan for “Phase 1”
 - Do you think the topics we cover in the initial plan will fill a gap in terms of skills or awareness needs (knowing that we will move on to more specific skills in “Phase 2”)?
 - Are there any additional topics you think we should cover?
 - Are there any topics we have included that you don't think are relevant?

3.3 Input from PARTHENOS WP leaders

Coupled with the expert talk and the peer review, PARTHENOS work package leaders were asked for their feedback to gain input on how the training plan can be implemented in accordance with the work that is going on in the PARTHENOS work packages.⁴ Work package leaders were requested via email and pointed to the training plan chapters about audiences, the teaching contents and the modes of delivery. They were asked to answer the following three questions on the two phases of the training plan and the delivery of training material:

- Do you think that topics within your work in PARTHENOS are satisfactorily represented in this phase of the training plan?
- What topics have you found so far in your work in PARTHENOS that you feel require training at a general level?
- How might the topics from your work package be best represented in this training? (Summer/Winter Schools, online interactive training, expert seminars, etc.)

People were also requested to identify issues, outputs or topics that they want to include in “Phase 2” of the training plan, which is on the more specific set of training modules that mainly derive from the PARTHENOS work packages.

4. Assessment of training plan

The following section provides a summary of the results derived from the three approaches presented in the previous chapter. Feedback is structured according to the topics / chapters of the training plan. Feedback derived from the expert focus group and peer reviews are

⁴ This input was requested to facilitate further work in PARTHENOS WP7 Task 7.2 but provides information on the assessment of the initial training plan as well.

presented in one section, followed by the input from the PARTHENOS work package leaders.⁵

Assessment of the background of the training plan development and overarching principles (chapters 2 and 3 of D7.1)

The overarching principles for the PARTHENOS training programme include a two-step approach based on “Phase 1” and “Phase 2” that concentrates on the education and recruitment of facilitators to train the trainers. Regarding the modes of delivery of the teaching content, the focus is on asynchronous delivery of online materials, some printed outputs, the organisation of face to face events together with cooperating partners whenever possible, and the distinction between the “need to know about” and the “need to know how to do”. From the humanities researchers’ perspective, the underlying approach of the training plan is a valid one. The “Phase 1” and “Phase 2” distinction has been assessed as being “... a practical and realistic way of approaching the subject”. This goes in line with the evaluation of the other experts as well. “Overall the approach is well thought-out and valid.”

The ‘train the trainers’ approach has been commented on as being a useful approach, particularly because there are longer-term and sustained networks, such as DARIAH, which can facilitate and disseminate the materials from a fixed-term project. This assessment applies to all experts.

Regarding the asynchronous mode of content delivery some slightly critical remarks were made from the researchers’ point of view. They admitted (in the expert talk as well as in the peer review) that the flexibility of asynchronous training is a considerable advantage. However, they raised concerns regarding the barrier of accessibility of asynchronous training programmes as they will probably face the same issues of access and uptake that all online resources face. At the current time, it is unclear to the researchers how the content will be made available, sustainable and how it will circumvent the issue of relevance.

The most discussed aspect of chapters 2 and 3 was the need for raising awareness of RIs. The focus of discussions centred on the question of whether it is actually still necessary to distinguish communities that use RIs from those that do not. In particular, Humanities

⁵ This is mainly because of the different questions that have been addressed to the PARTHENOS external people and the project members themselves.

researchers pointed out that a division of “Digital Humanists and Digital Humanists who use infrastructures might not be a considerable one” anymore. This point has been made by several persons and has been linked to the different career stages. The experts recommend a careful examination of how the career stages (early, mid and advanced carrier) relate to the engagement with the notion and use of infrastructures. It is not necessarily true that the idea of increasing digital maturity along the typical career trajectory is present anymore. The experts’ experiences revealed that it is not unusual for younger, less established researchers to be more advanced in regard to applying digital methods and usage of RIs in comparison to their more senior and established peers.

Audiences (chapter 4 of D7.1)

The breakdown of target groups / audiences has been evaluated as being clear and sufficient by the majority. The description of the four target groups has been assessed as being elaborated and reflecting the complexities within these groups.

However, one reviewer from the Cultural Heritage (CH) sector suggested to describe the areas / disciplines in more detail that make up the CH audience. Based on experiences from the EHRI (The European Holocaust Research Infrastructure) project, it is recommended that the training plan should rethink the role an archivist might play and to analyse if it might be worth addressing them separately.

Both the Expert Focus Group and Peer Reviewers noted that, particularly from the computer scientists perspective, the decision to go for a wide audience including technically-orientated researchers was strongly supported, and considered that it was especially worth investing effort to set up communication channels between computer scientists and humanities researchers. An additional recommendation coming from a computer scientist was that it might be worth elaborating on the target group of technical developers. It was recommended to discuss if a distinction between technical developers that are engaged in advancing the state of the art in computer science with digital humanities infrastructures and those who are engaged in the development and maintenance of digital tools or infrastructures as an enduring service should be taken into account in the second iteration of the training plan.

Teaching contents and modes of delivery (chapters 5 and 6 of D7.1)

Chapters 5 and 6 of the initial training plan were rated solid, coherent and well thought out by all the experts. The four described topics are all relevant and important. Data sharing,

knowledge creation, and sustainability were assessed as being the core aspects of dealing with RIs.

When it comes to the very concrete teaching contents, subject specific needs were highlighted. One example is the need for more language-related training as offered in the European Summer University (ESU) workshops “XML-TEI encoding, structuring and rendering” or “Compilation, Annotation and Analysis of Written Text Corpora. Introduction to Methods and Tools” have been mentioned explicitly.

More input on security issues such as authorisation and authentication as well as on sustainability were mentioned from the computer scientists’ point of view.

Regarding the modes of training delivery, it was suggested that the training plan should consider “hands on sessions” and to place emphasis on the linkage of theoretical work and existing projects, particularly for people at the early stage of their career.

Even if the overall teaching content has been evaluated very positively, the need to elaborate on the concrete aspects of the “Phase 1” modules was mentioned. This point includes ideas on how to precisely make clear how the modules differ in content from that already available on other websites and to think about an additional aspect, namely the dimension of how to promote the life cycle of engagement in RIs in general. That means how to stimulate and motivate the mentioned target groups to actively participate in a “true sharing ecosystem through infrastructures”.

The overall assessment from the PARTHENOS work package leaders regarding the training plan was very positive. The “Phase 1” and “Phase 2” approach appears sensible to all, especially when taking into account the progress in the project. Questions directed to the WP leaders align mainly on the teaching content and modes of delivery aspects of the training plan. The concrete input from them depends heavily on the current status of work and the further planning in the work packages. For several reasons, not all PARTHENOS work packages started work at the same time and are therefore currently at different levels when it comes to the actual and precise outputs. Taking this into account, the input for the initial training plan varies in granularity from WP to WP.

Do you think that topics within your work in PARTHENOS are satisfactorily represented in this phase of the training plan?

Since there was close cooperation with the PARTHENOS work package leaders during the development of the plan, and, therefore, they were informed all along about the underlying concepts and steps that resulted in the initial training plan, it is not surprising that their evaluation according to the question on how well they see their topics represented in “Phase 1” of the initial train plan is overwhelming positive.

WP2 acts as a link between all work packages and plays a pivotal role. It actually does not develop its own services or tools but concentrated on delivering a project-wide knowledge base and collecting use cases to enable the other work packages to start their work. For this work package it is somewhat challenging to find these kind of topics in the training plan. However, work from WP2 can be found in the training plan, mainly in the “Phase 1” module on “Humanistic Knowledge Creation and Research Processes”, especially when it comes to the process of knowledge generation in the humanities.

Main issues like the advantages of common standards for sharing data, interoperability, the role of relevant communities and institutions in standards recommendations are the centre of work in WP4 and can be located in the “Phase 1” module “Sharing Data With and Through Research Infrastructures” as well as in the short videos (see section 5.4).

The PARTHENOS work package 5 is about the definition of a conceptual architecture of a RI as well as on a model for representing the resources handled by such an architecture. Main aspects of that are seen in the “Infrastructure101” module - to raise the awareness of the potential of RIs within the humanities and to explain their functionalities to the new users. There is a second link between work in WP5 and the initial training plan which is located in the “Phase 1” module on “Humanistic Knowledge Creation and Research Processes”. This module will fit with the content of the brochure, in the sense that the humanistic knowledge generation process will be tightly coupled with a RI, and vice versa.

The topics dissemination and scientific communication, main topics of WP8, are well covered in the “Phase 1” module on “Sustainability for Research Infrastructures”. Regarding sustainability, WP7 team is inspired to take into account that sustainability is often

dependent on maximising socio-economic, political and cultural impact which could be made more explicit in the second iteration of the training plan.

What topics have you found so far in your work in PARTHENOS that you feel require training at a general level?

A main aspect in WP2 was the collection of user requirements in and for RIs. To facilitate work in WP2 CNR provided an online tutorial to the PARTHENOS members participating on how to write use cases. Thus, the aspect of user requirements handling by research infrastructures is something that could require training at a more general level.

Since the “Standard Survival Kit” (SSK) developed by WP4 will not be used as a standards catalogue, it is worth considering how to highlight the role standards can play in any researcher’s project from the arts and humanities, at each step of the research data lifecycle.

Training on how to measure, maximise and demonstrate impact, and in particularly non-academic impact, is useful for the work in WP8.

How might the topics from your work package be best represented in this training? (Summer/Winter Schools, online interactive training, expert seminars, etc.)

This question was most difficult to answer for the WP leaders since it requires a very concrete picture of the results that, in some cases, will be delivered only in the second half of the project. However, for the soon to be delivered SSK, high level training, both online and face-to-face, is suggested. As the SSK will provide a very wide range of standards and resources, it appears difficult to give complete training materials covering every use case. Thus, high level training might be the only solution.

Further discussions with the WP leaders and WP7 members are scheduled for this year to find out how to best integrate the PARTHENOS results into a common training plan and how to distribute and deliver training material accordingly.

5. First implementations and their assessment

The implementation of the initial training plan is an ongoing process. Due to the PARTHENOS schedule of reports and milestones the implementation is based on the initial training plan, which was delivered in June 2016. Therefore, the assessment in this report is focused on the workshop held in July 2016 at the European Summer University in Leipzig and on an overview of existing but not yet finalised implementations of the initial training plan.

5.1 Workshop at European Summer University in Digital Humanities

The European Summer University in Digital Humanities⁶ (ESU) took place in July 2016. Part of this renowned summer university was a workshop with the title “Digital Research Infrastructures in the Humanities: How to use, build and maintain them” led by Dr. Jennifer Edmond. The teaching contents reflected the “Phase 1” modules of the initial training plan, slightly adjusted to the needs of the workshop participants. During this one-week workshop the participants undertook the following four modules:

- Introduction to infrastructures,
- Managing infrastructures,
- Harnessing and understanding the collaborations within infrastructures,
- Policies in infrastructures.

In preparation for the ESU, a brief questionnaire was developed to collect the attendees’ feedback on the topics in general and the module’s ability to enhance their daily work. As the number of participants was not that high (five) we have not conducted any deep statistical analysis of the responses. However, the results demonstrate a first impression of the attendees’ quality assessment on the relevance of the topics. The questionnaire can be found in the annex.

The participants of the workshop had heterogeneous backgrounds. Their primary field of research ranged from “Digital mapping for the humanities tool development” to “Project Management”, “Digital Humanities”, “DH Information Literacy” to “Historical information

⁶ http://www.culingtec.uni-leipzig.de/ESU_C_T/node/97

systems and DH”. In all, five people attended the workshop successfully. Three of five participants hold a PhD whereas the other two hold a M.A.

As one can clearly see from chart 1 attendees were fully satisfied with the outcome of the workshop as it met their expectations.

Chart 1: Rating of expectations

The selected teaching content for this module was intended to reflect actual working practice, and appears that this was matched well as 100% of the participants indicated that they will be able to apply this in one way or another to their ongoing work. (see chart 2)

Chart 2: Rating of applicability to ongoing work

The following three charts demonstrate that there was a high level of satisfaction with the workshop topics. The introduction to infrastructures (chart 3) as well as the segments of specific approaches to managing infrastructures (chart 4) and on harnessing and understanding the collaborations within infrastructures (chart 5) are all rated very useful or useful.

Chart 3: Rating of usefulness of introduction to infrastructures

Chart 4: Rating of segments of specific approaches to managing infrastructures

Chart 5: Rating of segments on harnessing and understanding the collaborations within infrastructures

The only small deviation in the participants rating can be detected when it comes to the policy section. Around 20% rated that section “neutral”, whereas 40% assessed it as “very useful” and 40% as “useful”. Reasons for the rating may vary but one can assume that the policy section might have been too specific or might have had too many prerequisites to fully understand it. It is also possible that those who took part in this workshop do not consider knowledge of policy within this field to be directly relevant to their own research or work. For this reason, we may need to consider if this is indeed relevant to be introduced as a full topic for certain audience types, and if so, how can we better present this so that they can appreciate its relevance more.

Chart 6: Rating of usefulness of policy section

It is important to remember, however, that given the low number of participants within this workshop (mostly by design as the ESU workshops are kept to small numbers to enable a better interaction between trainer and participants), the data gives only a very limited view of the evaluation of the workshop. One should avoid making generalisations from the results. However, we do see this as initially very promising, with the majority of the results indicating positive reactions to the modules. There are no hints from these results that could point to a topic that is of minor utility or not useful at all.

A further cooperation with ESU will be discussed in the course of the project within WP7.

5.2 “The Policymaker’s Guide to Research Infrastructures” brochure

One result of the initial training plan is a brochure “The Policymaker’s Guide to Research Infrastructures” that aims at a description of basic terms and concepts of RIs. The brochure will introduce the key concepts of RIs and key vocabulary in layperson’s language to enable

easy understanding of what a RI is and why policymakers should support them. The brochure had not been finalized yet but an initial draft has already been reviewed and commented upon.

5.3 Video lectures

The modules of the ESU have been video recorded and will be published later on as asynchronous teaching material on the PARTHENOS teaching website. Work on the video lectures is ongoing. An assessment will be forthcoming in the context of the second iteration of the training plan and its evaluation in WP7.

5.4 Short videos

In addition to the video lectures referring to the “Phase 1” modules, three short videos have been published⁷. The videos explain in an entertaining way what metadata, standards and RIs are, how they are used and what advantages they have for researchers in the arts and humanities. As the clips are online at the PARTHENOS YouTube channel but are not published or linked to another resource yet (e.g. the PARTHENOS training website), an assessment based on downloads or clicks has not been conducted up to now but will be undertaken in the context of the second iteration of the training plan and its evaluation in WP7.

6. Abbreviations

AA	Academy of Athens
CENDARI	Collaborative European Digital Archival Infrastructure
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institution
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DASISH	Data Service Infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities
DigCurV	Digital Curator Vocational Education Europe
DH	Digital Humanities
EHRI	The European Holocaust Research Infrastructure
ESU	European Summer University
FHP	University of Applied Sciences Potsdam

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AEnXZGRbmlg> and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-YCZcDqLybM>

HaS	Humanities at Scale
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSK	Standard Survival Kit
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
UCHP	University of Copenhagen

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8. Annex

“Digital Research Infrastructures in the Humanities: How to Use, Build and Maintain Them” Questionnaire

1. What is your primary field of research?

2. What is your highest research degree?

3. How did you find out about the workshop?

4. What were your expectations on the workshop?

5. The workshop content met my expectations

(Please indicate whether and to what extent you agree with the above statement. Mark only one oval.)

- strongly agree
- agree
- neutral
- disagree
- strongly disagree

6. The workshop content was applicable to my ongoing work

(Please indicate whether and to what extent you agree with the above statement. Mark only one oval.)

- strongly agree
- agree
- neutral
- disagree
- strongly disagree

7. How useful did you find the introduction to infrastructures (Day 1) in developing your understanding or work within a research infrastructure context? (Tick all that apply)

- very useful
- useful
- neutral
- of minor utility
- not useful at all

8. How useful did you find the segments of specific approaches to managing infrastructures (Day 2) in developing your understanding or work within a research infrastructure context? (Mark only one oval)

- very useful
- useful
- neutral
- of minor utility
- not useful at all

9. How useful did you find the segments on harnessing and understanding the collaborations within infrastructures (Days 3-4) in developing your understanding or work within a research infrastructure context? (Mark only one oval.)

- very useful
- useful
- neutral
- of minor utility
- not useful at all

10. How useful did you find the summary and policy section (Day 4) in developing your understanding or work within a research infrastructure context? (Mark only one oval.)

- very useful
- useful
- neutral
- of minor utility
- not useful at all

11. How could the workshop be improved in terms of delivery, structure, content or other aspects?